
Data Strategy for Ecological Long-Term Data in LTER-Austria

February 2026

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1. Introduction

Ecological long-term data are essential for evidence-based environmental and nature conservation policy. Their systematic collection, management, and provision enable a better understanding of ecological processes, a robust assessment of long-term environmental change, and the fulfilment of national and international reporting obligations. With the LTER-Austria network (“Long-Term Ecosystem Research”) and its involvement in eLTER¹, Austria has an established organisation for the collection, management, and analysis of these data.

This strategy paper aims to establish a national framework for the handling of ecological long-term data. It was jointly authored by the members of LTER-Austria under the editorial leadership of the Environment Agency Austria.

The data strategy pursues the goal of making data interoperable, quality-assured, and sustainably available – in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)² as well as relevant national and European requirements, particularly with regard to the eLTER Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI) currently under development. The advantage of interoperable environmental data lies in the fact that they are standardised, comprehensible, combinable, and reusable – both within an organisation and across institutions, sectors, and national borders – thereby enabling more (cost-)efficient use and added value from existing data, as well as higher data quality and comparability.

The present strategy is primarily addressed to

- public research institutions and universities
- operators of monitoring sites (especially LTER-Austria and eLTER)
- stakeholders in the field of environmental reporting (especially public authorities)

and applies to data collected within the framework of long-term ecological observation programmes and projects at sites within LTER-Austria – particularly in the context of air quality, soil, biodiversity, water, vegetation, and climate change. Many of the following recommendations, however, are of general applicability and can also be applied to sites outside LTER-Austria.

¹ <https://elter-ri.eu/>

² <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

2. Strategic Guidelines

In general, several recommendations can be made for the different aspects of data management. In principle, data should be managed and published in accordance with the FAIR principles. The overarching objective is to generate robust datasets that are usable and comparable across sites and monitoring programmes, and for which it is clearly identifiable how the data were collected and how their use is regulated. Specifically, this includes the following points:

2.1. Data Acquisition and Standardisation

- All LTER-Austria sites should be fully documented in the DEIMS³ site registry in accordance with the requirements of eLTER⁴ and LTER-Austria. Entries should be kept up to date, for example after a change of site managers or modifications to the survey design. DEIMS is used as the central site registry by eLTER, thus generating synergy effects.
- Surveys at these sites should be conducted consistently with established methods, standards, and protocols, e.g., according to the requirements of the eLTER Standard Observations. The methods used must be documented together with the collected datasets.
- Coordination with international monitoring programmes (e.g., eLTER RI, ICP IM, ICP Forests, NEC Directive), especially regarding the use of standardised measurement methods, is actively promoted within LTER-Austria.

2.2. Data Management and Long-Term Storage

- For the structured storage of data, certified storage solutions that comply with sustainability and data protection requirements are recommended, e.g., B2Share⁵, Zenodo⁶ or the eLTER Digital Asset Register (DAR)⁷. Depending on the platform used, additional points should be considered:
 - Datasets on B2Share should be published under the LTER Community⁸ and include the DEIMS.iD of the site (see Annex). This allows automatic harvesting of the data by the eLTER RI.
 - Datasets on Zenodo should be published under the eLTER⁹ respectively LTER-Austria¹⁰ communities. References to eLTER and the corresponding site should be included in the keywords. This enables automatic harvesting of metadata by the eLTER RI.

³ <https://www.deims.org>

⁴ <https://qa.deims.org> bzw. <https://deims.org/docs/lter.html>

⁵ <https://b2share.eudat.eu>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org>

⁷ <https://dar.elter-ri.eu>

⁸ <https://b2share.eudat.eu/communities/lter/>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/elter>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/communities/lter-austria>

- Datasets on the eLTER DAR should additionally include eLTER-relevant information, such as habitat or eLTER Standard Observation, in the designated fields.
- Metadata should generally be documented in a uniform, complete, and machine-readable manner (depending on the platform used and the dataset to be published). This includes:
 - The use of persistent identifiers (e.g., ORCID for individuals, ROR for organizations, DEIMS.iD for sites, DOIs for datasets and method descriptions) is recommended and in some cases required (for example within the framework of eLTER).
 - The explicit specification of the methods used regarding data collection, quality assurance (e.g., removal of implausible values), and any interpolation of the data.
- Data ownership and responsibilities for maintenance and updates must be clearly defined but generally lie with the site operators.

2.3. Quality assurance and Versioning

- At the start of projects related to LTER, quality standards regarding the length, completeness, and plausibility of the datasets to be created should be defined, documented, and followed.
- Tiered quality assurance measures (for raw data, observational data, cleaned data, derived data)¹¹, which should align with the standards of the eLTER RI, must be defined.
- Data gaps and uncertainties must be documented and made transparent.
- Changes to published datasets must be documented in a traceable manner. This can be done on the platforms mentioned above, such as B2Share or Zenodo, by adding new versions to existing datasets.
- The establishment of curatorial functions (data stewardship) or the designation of central contact persons for data management issues in each organisation is recommended.

2.4. Data Provisioning and Sharing

- Data should be published, wherever possible, under open licences (e.g., CC-BY 4.0). The use of restrictive licences should be avoided.
- Open file formats should be preferred over proprietary formats, i.e., CSV or GeoPackage instead of XLSX or Shapefile.
- The use of high-performance or storage-efficient formats is recommended unless otherwise specified. For large datasets (e.g., long-term data), using different formats

¹¹ https://vocabs.lter-europe.net/elter_cl/en/page/10754

can result in significant differences in storage requirements (e.g., netCDF or HDF5 instead of CSV, or FLAG instead of WAV).

- Unless otherwise specified, date and time information should use ISO 8601 and the UTC+1 time zone (i.e., without switching for daylight saving time), using standard formats—for example, `2025-01-01T12:00:00+01:00` for 12:00 PM on January 1, 2025, in Vienna.
- Data provision through web portals, such as the eLTER DAR, GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility¹², national data nodes, or dashboards with machine-readable interfaces, should be pursued.
- The publication of species occurrence data (e.g., from vegetation surveys, zoological assessments, or monitoring programmes) should be actively promoted.
 - GBIF is recommended as the platform for publishing biodiversity-related observational data. The data should be structured according to the Darwin Core standards and documented using the GBIF Backbone Taxonomy. Using this taxonomy also ensures interoperability with the corresponding eLTER Standard Observation “Vegetation Composition”.
- The periodic publication of data in the form of a data paper is recommended and should be pursued, for example at the end of monitoring or research projects.

¹² <https://www.gbif.org/>

3. Connections to Reporting Obligations and Legal Frameworks

LTER-Austria sites have both opportunities and obligations to publish data, both within and outside of eLTER. The data strategy aims to support the fulfilment of any reporting obligations by identifying potential synergies. A detailed overview of the participation of Austrian long-term monitoring sites in monitoring programmes is provided in Annex Tab. 2. This information is based on the entries in DEIMS (as of February 2025).

The most common reporting obligations for Austrian LTER sites arise from the World Glacier Monitoring Service – WGMS (17 sites), the Habitats Directive and Natura 2000 (14), the NEC Directive and ICP Forests (7 each).

Additionally, there are programmes with lower participation, such as the Global Observation Research Initiative in Alpine Environments – GLORIA (3), the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands (3), the Birds Directive (2009/147/EC) (2), the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP), and ICP Integrated Monitoring (1 each). A basic explanation of the relevant programmes and their data reporting requirements is provided below.

3.1 EU Legal Frameworks

- NEC Directive (2016/2284/EU)¹³: Long-term data support the assessment of air pollutant effects, critical loads, and nitrogen deposition (Art. 9). The main air pollutants are sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOCs), ammonia (NH₃), and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}).
- INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EG)¹⁴: Provision of Standardised Environmental Geodata.
- Habitats Directive (CD, 92/43/EEC)¹⁵:
 - Article 11: „Member States shall undertake surveillance of the conservation status of the natural habitats and species referred to in Article 2 with particular regard to priority natural habitat types and priority species.”
 - Reporting obligation every six years (“report under Art. 17”), coordinated by the European Environment Agency (EEA).
- Regulation (EU) 2024/1991 – Nature Restoration Law¹⁶
 - Standardised monitoring from 2028,
 - Regular progress reports (every two years),
 - Indicators for status, implementation of measures, and target achievement.

¹³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/2284/oj>

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/oj>

¹⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1992/43/oj>

¹⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1991/oj>

- Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 on the “prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species”¹⁷ protects the EU from invasive alien species by regulating their introduction, spread, and management. Member States are required to monitor species, implement control measures, and report relevant data to the Commission.
- Biodiversity Strategy for 2030¹⁸: Monitoring data form the basis for evaluating measures and tracking targets.
- Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)¹⁹: obliges EU Member States to implement integrated, cross-border water management, aiming to achieve and maintain a good ecological and chemical status of all surfaces, coastal, and groundwater bodies by 2027 at the latest.

3.2 International Programmes

- CLRTAP/ICP Integrated Monitoring: Obligation to collect long-term data on air, soil, and biodiversity.
- CLRTAP/ICP Forests: Long-term Forest monitoring to assess the impacts of air pollution on forest ecosystems (Level I & II).
- UNEP/SDG-Monitoring: Contribution to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 15 – Life on Land.

3.3 National Strategies and Laws

The following national initiatives and laws provide a legal and thematic framework for the data strategy in Austria:

- Biodiversitätsstrategie Österreich („Biodiversity Strategy Austria“) 2030+²⁰
 - is a national programme for the conservation and enhancement of biological diversity in Austria, aligned with the objectives of the EU Biodiversity Strategy. It comprises a ten-point programme with quantitative and qualitative targets and measures for all habitats in Austria. One of its objectives is to improve the scientific basis for achieving and evaluating biodiversity targets.
- Umweltinformationsgesetz (“Environmental Information Act”) (UIG)²¹
 - The aim of this federal law is to inform the public about the environment, in particular by ensuring the right of access to environmental information held or made available by the information-obliged authorities, and by promoting the

¹⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2014/1143/oj>

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2020/380>

¹⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2000/60/oj>

²⁰ https://www.bmluk.gv.at/themen/klima-und-umwelt/natur-und-artenschutz-und-biodiversitaet/biologische-vielfalt/biodiversitaetsstrategie/biodiversitaetsstrategie_2030.html

²¹ <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10010766>

systematic and comprehensive availability and dissemination of environmental information.

- Immissionsschutzgesetz – Luft („Immission Control Act - Air“) (IG-L)²²
 - The objectives of this federal law include, among others, the permanent protection of human health, animal and plant populations, their communities and habitats, and their interactions, as well as the protection of cultural and material assets from harmful air pollutants, and the protection of humans from unreasonably disturbing air pollutants.
- Umweltkontrollgesetz (“Environmental Control Act“) (UKG)²³
 - Among other requirements, the Environmental Control Act (UKG) mandates the continuous observation, collection, and assessment of the state and development of the environment and environmental pressures, and the communication of the results of this environmental monitoring to the competent authorities, the National Council, the Federal Council, and the public.
 - The observation, collection, and assessment of the state and development of the environment must, in particular, cover the causes of hazardous, harmful, or nuisance environmental impacts and pressures, as well as the condition of the environment and ecosystems with their organisms, material cycles, and energy flows, taking a cross-media, integrative perspective.

²² <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10011027>

²³ <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10011109>

4. Overview of parameters to be prioritised for publication

Based on the reporting obligations mentioned and the general measurement programmes of the sites, the following parameters have been identified as priorities for publication (Table 1), taking into account the recommendations listed above.

Synergies can particularly arise from the overlap in reporting for eLTER, the NEC Directive, ICP Forests and ICP Integrated Monitoring, the Habitats Directive, and, to a lesser extent, the World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS).

Apart from the parameters listed in Table 1, it is expected that, due to EU Regulation 2024/1991 (“Nature Restoration Law”), there will be a stronger obligation for biodiversity monitoring in the future, including additional methods such as eDNA. Such extended biodiversity monitoring would also be covered by the corresponding eLTER Standard Observations (“Acoustic Recording”, “eDNA Water”, and “eDNA Soil”) as well as the reporting via GBIF.

Tab. 1 Semantically Aggregated Parameters from Different Monitoring Programmes

Parameter	eLTER Standard Observations	ICP Forests/ICP Integrated Monitoring	NEC Directive	WGMS	Habitats Directive
Site data	x	x	x	x	x
Meteorology	x	x	x		
Depositions	x	x	x		
Soil Chemistry/Soil Properties	x	x	x		
Leaf-/Needle analyses	x	x	x		
Growth and Biomass	x	x			
Glacier Mass Balance	x			x	
Glacier Length Change	x			x	
Land cover and use	x				x
Vegetation Composition	x	x	x		x
Bioacoustic recordings (species occurrence)	x				x

5. Concluding Remarks

The availability and sustainable usability of ecological long-term data form a central foundation for evidence-based decision-making in support of effective environmental, nature, and climate protection. This strategy defines the framework for coherent, coordinated collection, management, and provision of these data.

It aims to strengthen ecological monitoring and biodiversity management in Austria - particularly with regard to the targeted use of synergies and the enhancement of (cost-) efficiency in reporting at both national and international levels.

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Annex

Tab. 2 Austrian Monitoring Sites on DEIMS.org and Their Associated Reporting Obligations (Status: February 2026) - the “eLTER” designation is currently based on the listing in the corresponding eLTER labelling document

<i>Site [DEIMS reference]</i>	<i>Reporting for</i>
Achenkirch-Mühleggerköpfl (ACH-Mue) [DEIMS]	
Agricultural Research and Education Centre Raumberg-Gumpenstein [DEIMS]	eLTER, Natura 2000
Blütenwald [DEIMS]	
Brandstatt Landslide Monitoring Site [DEIMS]	
Experimental Farm Gross-Enzersdorf [DEIMS]	
Forest-Atmosphere-Interaction-Research Site Obermieming [DEIMS]	
Fuchsenbigl [DEIMS]	
Fürstenfeld (FF) [DEIMS]	eLTER
Gesäuse National Park [DEIMS]	Natura 2000, eLTER, Global Observation Research Initiative in Alpine Environments (GLORIA)
Gesäuse-Johnsbachtal [DEIMS]	Natura 2000, eLTER
GLORIA Master Site Schrankogel (AT-SCH), Stubai Alps [DEIMS]	Global Observation Research Initiative in Alpine Environments (GLORIA), Global Mountain Biodiversity Assessment (GMBA)
Gossenköllesee [DEIMS]	Man and the Biosphere Programme (EuroMAB)
Gresten - Am Salcher Landslide Observatory [DEIMS]	
Hallstätter Glacier [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS), eLTER
Hintereisferner [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS), INTERACT
Hochjochferner [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Hochschwab (AT-HSW) GLORIA [DEIMS]	Global Observation Research Initiative in Alpine Environments (GLORIA)
Hofermühle Landslide Monitoring Site [DEIMS]	
Hydrological Open Air Laboratory HOAL Petzenkirchen [DEIMS]	eLTER
ICP_Forests_Austria, Jochberg (ICP_FO_AU17) [DEIMS]	NEC Directive (2016/2284), ICP Forests (Level II), eLTER
ICP_Forests_Austria, Mondsee (ICP_FO_AU11) [DEIMS]	NEC Directive (2016/2284), ICP Forests (Level II)
ICP_Forests_Austria, Murau (ICP_FO_AU16) [DEIMS]	NEC Directive (2016/2284), ICP Forests (Level II), eLTER
ICP_Forests_Austria, Mürzzuschlag (ICP_FO_AU15) [DEIMS]	NEC Directive (2016/2284), ICP Forests (Level II), eLTER
ICP_Forests_Austria, Unterpullendorf (ICP_FO_AU2) [DEIMS]	NEC Directive (2016/2284), ICP Forests (Level II), eLTER

Jamtalferner [DEIMS]	eLTER
Kalkalpen National Park [DEIMS]	Natura 2000, Ramsar Convention on Wetlands
Kaunertal: From glacier to community [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS), eLTER
Klausen-Leopoldsdorf Long term forest monitoring [DEIMS]	NEC Directive (2016/2284), ICP Forests (Level II), eLTER
Kleineiserkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Klosterwald [DEIMS]	
Kollerhube – Lehrforst [DEIMS]	
Landeggkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Laxenburg Schlosspark [DEIMS]	
Lehrforst Rosalia [DEIMS]	eLTER
LTER Biologische Station Neusiedler See [DEIMS]	Natura 2000, eLTER, FLUXNet
LTER Hohe Tauern National Park (NPHT) [DEIMS]	EUROPARC, Birds Directive (2009/147/EC), Natura 2000, eLTER
LTER NoeSLIDE [DEIMS]	
LTER Zöbelboden [DEIMS]	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP), ICP Integrated Monitoring, Natura 2000, NEC Directive (2016/2284), eLTER
LTSER Platform Austrian Central Alps (ACA) [DEIMS]	CarboEurope, FLUXNet, eLTER
LTSER Platform Eisenwurzen (EW) [DEIMS]	Global Observation Research Initiative in Alpine Environments (GLORIA), Natura 2000, eLTER
LTSER Platform Oberes Paznaun [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS), Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW), eLTER
LTSER Platform Pannonischer Raum [DEIMS]	EuroMAB, Natura 2000, Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, eLTER
Mullwitzkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS), eLTER
Nationalpark Neusiedler See – Seewinkel [DEIMS]	EUROPARC, Natura 2000, Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, UNESCO World Heritage Site, eLTER
Oberes Stubachtal [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Obergurgl [DEIMS]	Natura 2000
Ödenwinkelkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Piburger See [DEIMS]	NETLAKE Cost Action ES1201
Pristine Forest Rothwald (part of Dürrenstein Wilderness Area) [DEIMS]	Natura 2000
Puergschachen Moor [DEIMS]	eLTER, FLUXnet
Research Department for Limnology Mondsee [DEIMS]	Natura 2000, eLTER, UNESCO World Heritage Site
Rofental [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Rottenhaus / Grabenegg [DEIMS]	
Rutzendorf, MUBIL Trial [DEIMS]	

Sonnblick Observatory [DEIMS]	ACTRIS, INTERACT, WMO Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW), Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P), Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW), World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS), eLTER
Stubacher Sonnblickkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Stubai (combination of Neustift meadows and Kaserstattalm) [DEIMS]	CarboEurope, FLUXNet
Totenkopfkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Tyrolean High Mountains (Plattform) [DEIMS]	eLTER; siehe zugehörige Standorte
Tyrolean Lakes [DEIMS]	eLTER
Tyrolean Mountain Grassland and -Forest [DEIMS]	eLTER
Unterer Eisboden See [DEIMS]	
Unteres Riffelkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
Venedigerkees [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS), eLTER
Vernagtferner [DEIMS]	World Glacier Monitoring Service (WGMS)
WasserCluster Lunz [DEIMS]	eLTER, Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON)
WegenerNet Feldbach Region [DEIMS]	eLTER, International Soil Moisture Monitoring Network (ISMN)
Weitra (WEI) [DEIMS]	ICP Forests (Level I), eLTER
Wilderness Area Dürrenstein [DEIMS]	eLTER, Birds Directive (2009/147/EC), Natura 2000
Ziegelwald [DEIMS]	